

Probabilistic Neural Network on Higher Order Spectrum Classification

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Many tasks in classification and recognition system need to be performed in real time. While there are difficulties due the complexity of considered pattern, i.e., as the pattern becomes more complex the training set of pattern is insufficient to represent what will arise during tests. In our previous study, we characterized the Higher order spectrum (HOS) pattern property and its classification strategy. The HOS pattern is preferred to be used for some classification tasks, as for their interesting characteristic, i.e, higher dimensionality, Gaussian noise removal, and phase relation quantification. An appropriate feature extraction mechanism is certainly needed in order to quantize this HOS input pattern before classification. However, for a real time classification task, this well-developed feature extraction process should be adhered by a robust and fast classifier. In this study, we present the use of Probabilistic Neural Network(PNN) as Neural Classifier and compared it with conventional Back Propagation(BP) learning scheme. Both memorization and generalization comparison of those network are discussed as for developing a robust and fast speaker identification in noisy environment. It was shown that even using only a small size codebook, PNN can classify bispectrum pattern above 88% success rate and 36 times faster than BP

Keywords: higher order spectrum, probabilistic neural net, fast speaker identification

1. Introduction

Speaker identification has been the subject of active research for many years, and has many interesting applications where propriety of information is a concern [1][2]. This identification system provides an information as to whether a particular voice, for example recorded making a telephone call, or participating in a conversation recorded by a recording device, is that of a particular known person. Generally, using speech biometrics for identification system provides an inexpensive means of verifying who is accessing secured services, systems, and information.

In our previous study presented in [3], [4], [5], [6], [7] and [8] we developed a speaker identification system relied on bispectrum and trispectrum as selected speech features. The study has presented an efficient feature extraction mechanism through adaptive

codebook generation algorithm and PCA / Karhunen-Loeve transformation for feature's orthogonalization and dimensionality reduction. The most important point obtained from our previous study is that using higher order spectrum can be viewed as adding the dimensionality of the input pattern. Hence the higher order spectrum of different class has more probability to be separated than those commonly used power spectrum pattern. While it's seem will lead to the curse of dimensionality problem, it is not, since we deployed a feature's dimensionality reduction using Karhunen-Loeve transformation.

It was experimentally shown that higher recognition performance could be attained eventhough using only small number of codebook size and performed in a noisy environment. However, this system still required an expensive amount of computational time due

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to daunting gradient descent task of conventional BP learning scheme. As for the increasing demand of using this system for real time application, current study tried to alleviate the problem by proposing the used of PNN as a fast and robust (to additive noise) neural classifier.

2. HOS Feature Extraction

Currently, there are still not many works considering higher order spectrum of voice data, especially for speaker recognition task. However, HOS was tried to be used for throat disease detection [9]. In this study, we used bispectrum and trispectrum as selected discriminating features [10]. While these features extracted not only amplitude and frequency of considered signal, it also preserved phase information between frequency component. Beyond what can be estimated by power-spectrum analysis, this higher order spectrum has some figures of merit due to an available information regarding deviations from Gaussianity and presence of nonlinear phase relation. A direct, non-parametric bispectrum and trispectrum signal processing based on

$$C_N^x(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_{N-1}) = X(f_1)X(f_2) \cdots X^*(f_1 + f_2 + \dots + f_{N-1}) \quad (1)$$

was conducted. Where $X(f_i)$ is short term Fourier spectral at frequency f_i and $X^*(f_i)$ is complex conjugate of $X(f_i)$. While the bispectrum and trispectrum are can be viewed as third order and fourth order of Fourier autocorrelation, power spectrum is a special case of higher order spectrum, i.e., second order Fourier autocorrelation which can be estimated as

$$C_2^x(f) = X(f)X^*(f). \quad (2)$$

Qualitative comparison in term of robustness to additive Gaussian noise between power spectrum and bispectrum can be referred in [3].

Thoroughly, HOS feature extraction mechanism can be viewed in Table 1. This based on an adaptive codebook generation algorithm using SOFM and LVQ neural network, see [3] for detail. The computational cost for this vector

quantization is generally linear to the size of input pattern, $k O(n)$. Where the k depends on the number of training patterns, codebook channels, invoked epoch, and also the neighborhood size. In average, input section process take about 3 %, SOFM take about 67 % and LVQ process take about 30 % of the total computational cost.

Karhunen-Loeve transformation or subspace decomposition is applied on the higher order spectra feature after vector quantization. This transformation means to orthogonalize (increase the separability of the extracted feature) and to reduce its dimensionality. This transformation means to to extract feature's components, which account for 'most' variation in the original higher order spectrum signal.

Adaptive-Codebook-Generation()

1. Read magnitude bispectrum data samples from H speakers (only one sample for each speaker).
2. Normalize and take the average.

$$\bar{C}_3^x(f_1, f_2) = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H \frac{C_{3,h}^x(f_1, f_2)}{\max[C_{3,h}^x(f_1, f_2)]}$$

3. Map the coordinate $(f_1, f_2) \rightarrow (\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{n}_2)$ in range [0:1]
4. Do while $trial < \tau$ (τ : maximum number of trials)
5. $\zeta_1 \leftarrow \text{Rand}(0,1)$
6. $\zeta_2 \leftarrow \text{Rand}(0, \zeta_1)$
7. $\zeta_3 \leftarrow \text{Rand}(0, \max[|\bar{C}_3^x(\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{n}_2)|])$
8. For all points $(\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{n}_2)$ in symmetric bispectrum domain do steps 9-12
9. Find the closest $(\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{n}_2)$ to (ζ_1, ζ_2)
10. If $\zeta_3 > |\bar{C}_3^x(\mathbf{n}_1, \mathbf{n}_2)|$ then
11. take $(\zeta_1, \zeta_2), \mathbf{z} \leftarrow (\zeta_1, \zeta_2)$
12. else ignore (ζ_1, ζ_2)
13. Select the training input vector \mathbf{z} randomly.
14. Generate a general codebook \mathbf{m}_y , using SOFM
15. Determine class labels for each input vector
16. Improve the codebook using supervised LVQ algorithm.

Table 1. Adaptive Codebook Generation

3. PNN classifier

The PNN is related to BP primarily in structure. The structure of the PNN is a layered, feed-forward network, just like the BPN. The primary difference between the PNN and the BP network is in the operation of the units in the network. In the PNN, we implement a Bayesian decision strategy for classifying input vectors. This behavior is provided by using a Gaussian activation function on the pattern layer, combined with the operation of the summation units. The pattern units operate by computing the inner product of the input pattern vector and weight vector to each unit, just as in the BP. Here, however, we must ensure that the input vector has been normalized prior to presentation to the network. [11].

In essence, the network operates by summing the outputs from all pattern units, which, because of the Gaussian activation function, serve to classify the input pattern into classes. Thus, the PNN is actually computing the *a posteriori* probability distribution function for a single class, evaluated at the point defined by the input pattern. This behavior is useful in classification applications, where we want to estimate the likelihood that a new pattern is a member of any of our predefined classes.

One of the principal advantages of the PNN paradigm is that it is very much faster than well-known BP paradigm for problems in which the incremental adaptation time of BP is a significant fraction of total computation time. Moreover, according to a reported work [12] the classification accuracy was roughly comparable, i.e., about 82% to 85% respectively for BP and PNN.

4. Result of Experiment

In this study we aimed at improving the speed of learning while maintain high recognition rate of our speaker identification. The speech data consists of an isolated word 1.28 s length

sampled at 11 kHz. Five male and 5 female speaker utter in an assumed noise free condition for 20 times. The uttered word is an Indonesian word ‘/ma/ /jyu/’ which has an english meaning ‘-forward’. This word is used as we means to give a controlled access to our dog-tracker robot. For the BP network, the used parameters was refered to an optimum setting which is conducted in [6] and [7]. While the number of hidden units used in this experiment is varied between 20, 30 and 50 units.

The recognition performance comparison between BP (with 50 hidden units) and PNN on bispectrum classification was performed in several different additive Gaussian noise level using a same number of input. The result can be observed in Figure 1 and 2.

The result of BP network shown the average recognition rate is 81.9% for speech without noise addition, 81.8%, 78.8%, and 70.4% respectively for 20dB, 10dB, dan 0dB noise level. This performance can be enhanced by changing some its learning parameters i.e., adding the number of hidden units, modifying momentum and learning rate, but those improvement was not significantly different from those obtained in Figure 2.

For PNN learning, it is can be shown that testing result on data without noise addition is the strong point of this network. This is because of those ‘clean’ training input are directly used to initialize weights of the network, i.e., those clean input pattern become representative (center) of the cluster. Therefore, the recognition rate for this non-added (noise) data is almost 100%. For SNR 20dB noise addition, a similar result compared to without noise addition was observed, i.e., about 97%. As the noise level is increased to 10dB and 0dB, apparently the recognition result is still high, above 90% when using above 98 codebook size.

The input pattern obtained as the size of the codebook was getting large, also has been tested on this experiment. Generally, as the codebook’s size increased, the recognition result will also increased asymptotically. Due to space limitation we will present this result in another

paper. Finally, we can observe the computational time comparison between BP and PNN as is shown in Table 2 and 3.

Figure 2. BP recognition performance

Codebook Size	time (hour)		Codebook Size
	Bispectrum	Trispectrum	
50	0.209722	0.250833	54
128	0.186111	1.357500	128
242	0.786389	0.319722	250
450	1.377222	0.992500	432
648	1.118056	1.135278	686

Tabel 2. Computational time for BP (hidden=50)

Codebook Size	Time (second)		Codebook Size
	Bispectrum	Trispectrum	
50	20	22	54
128	47	40	128
242	51	62	250
450	119	74	432
648	161	149	686

Table 3. Computational time for PNN

5. Conclusion

This study has presented some proliferation of a HOS based speaker identification system. It was shown that the used of PNN experimentally enhanced its recognition performance while also preserved its robustness to additive Gaussian

noise. In the future we plan to compare also its generalization for unlearned voice and put the system in text-dependent mode. We believe that this approach will broaden a general perspective for future speaker identification system.

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Research interests:

1. Higher Order Spectrum analysis.
2. Pattern Recognition
3. Perceptual Grouping on 3D vision and modeling